

2 HP is enough.

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Abstract:

Miyawaki planning and engineering is extended to social forestry applications in agroforestry, leading to the architectural planning of a resilient spiritual community with Brikawood based Pyramids, and a resilient five level Miyawaki forest with edible and medicinal trees and shrubs, leading to a high food security emergent from the agroforestry practices and plant acupuncture techniques. The low energy intensive and outdoor ready technologies prove the sustainability of the approach in a return of druidic and droidatic sciences.

Keywords: Druidry, Droidatic, Brikawood, Biolite, peltier, solar lamps, biomass briquettes , agroforestry, epaper.

What:

The use of animal power is transitioned to a system of electric machines and a motocross based ecological sustainability, in a minimalism on low watt usability, low watt usually depicted as in a derogatory context is reformulated in A.I based smartness as energy conservation and the prudent use of the joule, a transhumanism in energy and a better, sensitive and sustainable solution. A better innovation.

In this paper, a technology of synchrony with the elements in true sustainable design principles completes the circular design in time, of the timeless droids and druidic sciences. This is in essence the work of Akiro Miyawaki, where humans are the medium of Nature, reclaiming and restoring land.

How:

Akiro Miyawaki's Philosophy (*The Miyawaki Method: A Better Way to Build Forests?*, 2019) calls for engineered forest, achieved through Mapillary like A.I based tools with design principles like MFA II, [Bheemaiah A.K. 2019](#) invented by the author, for a minimalism , the author calls Practical Shambhala, a work theology to complement the knowledge of Vajrayana.

Main Points:

1. The need for technology in synchrony with the elements, seen as an end to the struggle and suffering in neo human civilizations.
2. Practical examples of such technology, ranging from nano-fibre based, antimicrobial and anti wetness fabrics, Outdoors ready electric wagons, with less than 2HP power, and tablets with a hybrid cloud, both web2 and web3, with a quantum ising model based coherence.
3. Agroforestry and Miyawaki based landscaping as the culmination of human engineering, a completion of the cycles of innovation in a return to druidry and droidary.
4. Low watt is smart in druidry and with lower energy requirements, energy is sustainable.

Introduction.

At Mutter Gottlich, primitivism and minimalism are often revisited, in an almost Amish like existence, with an agroforestry approach to agriculture, the forest is suddenly alive with numerous possibilities for concepts as strange as food security, in a spectrum between an intentional ecommerce economy, that remains with the mainstream, not marginalised and the primitivism coupled with minimalism is a design of engineered forests or Miyawakis, with agroforestry.

The practice borrows from standard forest management and afforestation principles of thinning, with the exception that trees are transplanted in the thinning process and reused in Miyawaki planting using a range of AI driven technologies from smart ATVs and UTVs, with tree spades, scalable to Volvo FMX 440 Transplanters.

A five or more level Miyawaki is easily implemented and planned.

A Miyawaki coupled with a careful planning of a stable distribution of species grouping and population dynamics to minimize the loss of plants, and human effort can lead to stable agroforestry solutions with perennial solutions, perennial fruits, vegetables, berries, mushrooms and salad sources. Scalable perennial grasses can also be included, so food grains could be perennial too, one can easily imagine varieties of bamboo, flowering not once every 11 years, but periodically leading to edible bamboo grains, ancestral perennial rice, scaled and several perennial grasses, so drought and pest resistance, they may outlive us.

Energy is Sustainable.

Energy is indeed sustainable, with sources like biomass briquettes from fallen leaves, solar usb garden lamps, and a Biolite like peltier based stove scaled to generate 60 watts or more of power, sustainability is minimalist and cost effective. Solar lights easily scale to a comfortable 5 watts, while a Biolite like wood stove generates enough power to recharge an ATV . The ATV with at least 1 HP power and a ton capacity, available off the shelf replaces the need for animal power, yet providing the convenience of animal powered solutions, with an autonomous follower mode, where carts are imprinted to follow free ranging guide animals or humans, even homing pigeons are trained to operate these carts.

Miyawaki Planning.

(D. Bheemaiah Anil Kumar, 2019) describes the use of a modified version of Mapillary for stable plant population estimation for Miyawaki planning, based on the natural population dynamics.

Beyond IP68

Truly outdoors technologies need a robust science, of weather proof technologies and resilience, e-paper, Biolite like stoves, fallen leaf based briquettes and simple electric karts, form some of the robust outdoors ready technologies.

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The author was perplexed by the futility of living, the struggle in the inversion of the order of life, life had rendered the author to

not just the dry land but the habitation of the indoors, in a home and an automobile, and the media of a display unit, in so little land, dead and devoid of the living, of the indoors and the monitors and television displays, the author saw suffering and an illusion of control, colonialism and death/genocide, much like Sakhyamuni or gutamma buddha, after years of meditation on the futility of the struggle, and the ultimate victory of water, and sea water in an instantaneous destruction of this dryness, the electronic technologies and all the dry land, the land in habitation, was the true awakening, a need to live feral, naturally with the elements, only the feral races, were in peace with the elements, the neptunism, and water was life, needing technology in synchrony with the elements, clothing and habitation, electronics that synchronized and inherited from the elements

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The search for such technology leads to simple solutions, an ATV for mobility, quantum tablets for computing, one with the force with the Qi and a hybrid web2 and web3 architecture(A. K. D. Bheemaiah, 2019) and a pyramid with lego architecture(*Brikawood*, n.d.), at an elevation, in the canopy of trees, clothing that is dirt and wetness invariant, with gecko feet based technologies. ([Deepti N\)\(Ray S.S et. al.\)](#))

Food From AgroForestry

The staple diet in the Himachal Pradesh region of the Indian Himalayas consist of vegetables, rice, pigeon pea based curry and a flat bread called the roti, all the ingredients for these food products are obtained from perennial agroforestry

sources, this includes edible leaves and vegetables, flour from edible varieties of bamboo, rice from perennial rice, which grows throughout the year, and the pigeon pea shrub that is perennial and grows to 12 feet or higher. This diet is the staple food of the masses and is easily amenable to agroforestry leading to a high food security in Miyawaki based agroforestry engineering.

Discussion.

The design of a sustainable, low energy intensive primitivist village for Buddhism based spiritual retreats in the isolation of pristine primary Miyawakis with a self-sufficiency in energy and material needs is described. The low energy requirements would lead to a higher index of spiritual harmony and inner peace. A staple diet based completely from agroforestry, which is sustained by the Miyawaki, needing no agricultural inputs, like pesticides, fertilizers or irrigation is described. A proposal for a concrete implementation of these Miyawakis and an analysis of their role in resilience is the topic of future publication.

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